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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This deliverable (D1.6 Methodology) builds upon D1.3 - User Journey Maps and User Guidance (Rudolph et al., 2023b), D1.4 - Methodology beta version (Odic et al., 2023a), and D1.5 - Methodology pre-validation report (Odic et al., 2023b), and is an update arising from activities carried out between November 2023 and July 2025 and consequent improvements to the process. It describes the workflow of the INDUSAC piloting, which had several phases. In the Planning phase, companies identified a challenge and students/researchers were made aware of the project opportunities. In the Onboarding phase, companies registered on the INDUSAC platform and issued a Challenge. During the Search phase, students/researchers selected appropriate Challenges, assembled co-creation teams and submitted Motivation Letters, and the companies carried out the selection of co-creation teams to solve their Challenges. During the Project phase, selected co-creation teams proceeded with solving the Challenge with assistance from the company. INDUSAC provided provide students, researchers and companies with tailored guidance packages to support their co-creation experience. Finally, during the Offboarding phase, co-creation projects were completed and both companies and students/researchers provided feedback on the process. The process ended when the company confirmed the completion of the co-creation project (the submission of the Solution to the Challenge) including the reporting duties, and researchers and students received the INDUSAC certificate whereas participating student members of the co-creation teams were in addition eligible to receive funding up to 1,000 EUR gross per student (with a maximum of 3,000 EUR gross per team). Challenges and Motivation Letters were submitted continuously, with several cut-off dates at which collected Motivation Letters were reviewed and co-creation teams were selected to carry out the co-creation projects within four to eight weeks. The methodology also presents the Invitation to universities, Call for companies and Call for students and researchers, where terms and conditions for all participants are listed, including the aspects of geographical coverage, gender balance and internationalisation, status requirements, as well as confidentiality and intellectual property. The INDUSAC methodology was successively improved until the project's end and successfully implemented to achieve the project's goals.

Keywords: INDUSAC, academia-industry cooperation, methodology, co-creation

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BCG	Boston Consulting Group
BIC	BYDGOSZCZ INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER TOOL VALLEY
CCIPB	PECS-BARANYAI KERESKEDELMI ES IPARKAMARA
CET	Central European Time
CHE	Chemistry
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology
CV	Curriculum vitae
ECA	European Court of Auditors
ECO	Economic Sciences
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East GmbH
ENG	Information Science and Engineering
ENV	Environment and Geosciences
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FM	Final Milestone meeting
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IAC	Industry-academia collaboration
IBAN	International bank account number
ID	Identification
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
INNO	Innoget / INNOVAWIN 2006 SL
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KO	Kick-Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIF	Life Sciences
M	Month
MAT	Mathematics
MS	Milestone Meeting
MSc	Master of Sciences

NACE	Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne)
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
NR	Number
OLAF	European Anti-Fraud Office
PCA	Pre-defined collaborative approach
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PHY	Physics
SME	Small-to-Medium-Sized Enterprise
SOC	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications
SWOT	Strengths weaknesses opportunities threats
UK	United Kingdom
VAT	Value added tax

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I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable (D1.6 Methodology) describes the workflow of the INDUSAC piloting and represents the final version of the deliverable, updated with improvements following the activities since the first version of the deliverable was submitted in October 2023. It is intended to visualise the workflow of INDUSAC piloting. The workflow was refined throughout the project (for example, following the first rounds of co-creation projects when further knowledge had been gained). The objective of this deliverable is to describe the process from inviting universities to promote the project among students and researchers, companies to issuing Challenges, and students and researchers to solve Challenges, until the finalisation of the co-creation projects by the co-creation teams of students and researchers.

Upgrades to the Methodology beta version (upgrades from D1.4 to D1.6 (M14))

The deliverable is an upgrade of D1.4 Methodology: beta version (Odic et al., 2023a) based on the D1.5 Methodology Pre-validation Report (Odic et al., 2023b). D1.5 was a result of a virtual workshop demonstrating the methodology and the INDUSAC platform to representatives of students, researchers and companies and collecting their questions and remarks. The conclusion of the workshop was that no major changes are required to the beta version of the methodology, so this deliverable (that is, the main scheme of the project) is not substantially different compared to D1.4. Two points arose from D1.5 that required additional clarification: First, the recommendation to make sure that roles and expectations on the side of researchers / students as well as the side of companies are clear, has been included in Section 2.6.2 and Annex 3 (Call for Companies), explaining implementation of the project. Second, a question arose whether it is possible to apply with several Motivation Letters but then cancel some of them in favour of others, which deserved establishing a strong policy on the freedom of selecting Challenges to apply for. The recommendation to apply with a single strong Motivation Letter rather than three less elaborated ones has been included in Annex 5 (Call for Students and Researchers).

Apart from D1.5, this deliverable was additionally upgraded based on in-consortium discussions and clarifications, for example (i) including the administration required for FSTP payment in the project's timeline (Section 2.1.1 and Annex 5 – Call for Students and Researchers) and guidelines (Section 2.6.8 and Annex 5), (2) explaining the model co-creation process in more detail (Section 2.6.2), (3) limiting the role of the Evaluation Board to reviewing rejected Solutions (Section 2.6.7), and (4) detailing the criterium for gender balance in Annex 5 (Call for Students and Researchers).

Upgrades from the previous version (D1.6, M14) to this final version of „INDUSAC Methodology”, D1.6, M35

In addition to building on the beta version, this deliverable is a further upgrade of its previous version (D1.6 Methodology, M14; Odic et al., 2023a) containing the following key modifications:

- aims of the project are listed in detail to accurately reflect the Grant Agreement (pages 11-13)
- the first two cut-off dates for students to submit Motivation Letters were extended, and additional cut-off dates were added resulting in nine cut-off dates in total, with the final cut-off date set to 15.04.2025 (pages 17, 18, 25, 61)
- for clarity, detailed timelines for individual co-creation project rounds were replaced with a general timeline that was followed for each cut-off date (page 18)
- a rule was added to the Call for Students and Researchers that a student or researcher cannot participate in more than one Motivation Letter submitted to the same Challenge (pages 24, 33)
- fourth cut-off date for companies to submit Challenges (15.03.2025) was added to the Call for Companies (pages 21, 49, 54)
- a rule was added to the Call for Companies and the Call for Students and Researchers that if the company, for any reason (including non-responsiveness or inability to support co-creation projects), did not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter would be nullified (and therefore would not count into the quota of maximum of three Motivation Letters per student) and each team member would have the option to participate in another Motivation Letter for a different Challenge. Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time were closed for further applications. (pages 21, 26, 52, 65)
- The FSTP declaration (Annex 18) has also been slightly updated, to (i) include the co-creation team ID number, (ii) list the full date requirements for six potential student members of the team, (iii) more clearly indicate where the researcher members of the team should be listed, and (iv) indicate signature lines for six potential student members of the team. Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 18 since the Annex reflects the Declaration in its final form, as it is sent out for signing. (page 26)
- to illustrate the process more clearly, structure of the Monitoring Report is added to this document (page 29)
- the taxation procedure was simplified (pages 33, 67)
- Structure and roles of the Evaluation Board and the Mentoring Committee were slightly redefined while maintaining the core idea of their function (pages 35, 36)
- questions from the form for evaluation of Solutions were added to the Questionnaire for companies after completion of the co-creation project (page 101)

- a question was added to the Questionnaire for companies after completion of the co-creation project asking for a short description of the project results, and probability of recommendation of participation in this kind of project to the company's peers (page 104)
- certain suggestions by students, researchers, and companies, which were collected by the Mentoring Committee, were implemented during the project but did not change the workflow or had a major impact on methodology

This document is structured as follows; Section 1 outlines the context. Section 2 explains the workflow with a stepwise description of each process step. Section 3 explains the definitions and roles within the co-creation process. Section 4 outlines the social sciences (SSH) aspects. Section 5 (the Annexes) provides the forms and templates.

1.1 About the INDUSAC Project

INDUSAC's main objective was to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim was to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, the project piloted the mechanism's two main components: a methodology (this deliverable) and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey. The INDUSAC methodology provided the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stood as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC also created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including around 270 companies, 950 students and 180 researchers.

The aims of the INDUSAC project, listed as KPIs of individual Objectives, related to the methodology (namely, Objectives 1, 3 and 5), and the levels of KPIs reached, were as follows:

- under Objective 1 (To develop and optimise a mechanism for Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations involving students and researchers from across Europe (from at least 3 different Member States or Associated Countries) in collaboration with industry innovation professionals.):

Measured by	Result
A minimum average satisfaction score of 3.8 out of 5 in the Likert scale multiple aspect questionnaire from those company representatives, students and researchers involved in the piloting of projects.	On average, students and researchers' satisfaction scored 4.28 (85.7 %) for the INDUSAC process and 4.33 (86.7 %) with the INDUSAC platform. Companies' satisfaction scored 4.05 (81.0 %) for the process and 4.03 (80.7 %) for the platform.

- under Objective 3 (To build a dynamic, inclusive, EU-wide and territorially balanced, in-project scale community of universities, students, companies, clusters and associations registered on the INDUSAC online platform (Objective 2) which will enable the piloting of the INDUSAC mechanism (Objective 1).):

Measured by	Result
Reaching at least 2,000 students and researchers registered from 30 research organisations, 100 companies, and at least 3 KICs and 15 industrial clusters offering long-term access to at least 10,000 SMEs and covering at least 14 Member States, with a total minimum user representation of 60% from widening countries.	We received 37 letters of support from universities and research organisations. More than 580,000 individuals were reached out to, out of which more than 28,000 were from companies and more than 550,000 were students or researchers, while 115 were from 4 KICs and 394 from industrial clusters (see Table 2). Around 1,400 individuals (270 companies, 180 researchers and 950 students from more than 40 universities / research organisations) registered on the INDUSAC platform, covering 27 member states and user representation of around 67% from widening countries.
Achieving a minimum average of 7 connections per month from all users and an average time on the site of 5 minutes.	<p>average number of website visits per month: 1,611</p> <p>average time spent on website per visit: 1.23 min (1 m 14 s)</p> <p>average number of platform logins per month: 277</p> <p>average time spent on platform per visit: 6.63 minutes (6 m 38 s)</p>

Achieving a minimum of 3,000 members by project end, covering the sectors and cross-cutting areas addressed	about 1400 members (950 students, 180 researchers and 270 companies) have registered on the platform.
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- under Objective 5 (To extract from the pilot activity all the necessary data and information and to analyse and process it to demonstrate the effectiveness of the INDUSAC mechanism in achieving the outcomes aimed for by it and the long-term sustainability of offering it to the EU academic and business community):

Measured by	Result
Demonstration of the feasibility of running the IAC mechanism with less than €3,000 per co-creation team	A total of 166 co-creation teams received 3,000 EUR or less each.
At least 70% of students and researchers participating reporting at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism	Over 87 % of students and researchers participating reported significant development in negotiation and conflict management, and experience in working with companies and international teams skills, as well as creativity, critical thinking, time management, and leadership. 90% of students and researchers reported overall improvements of skills.
At least 70% of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the program as being suitable)	The overall percentage of relevance (evaluated by scale on 1 to 5 and considering the 4 and 5 grades as representing 'relevance') showed a trend of increase over time but was on average 82.5%.
At least 80% of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a program to their peers	Overall, 89.9% of students and researchers would likely or highly likely recommend this programme. This percentage is slightly higher for companies (93.5%) albeit with a smaller sample (92 company replies vs. 574 student / researcher replies).

1.2 About the INDUSAC Co-creation Process

The objectives of co-creation were to promote and push the use of the INDUSAC platform for cross-border EU-wide matching challenges of companies and solutions by students/researchers. The platform played a dual role. On the one hand, it provided a digital matchmaking and networking space that enabled the connection between companies and co-creation teams. On the other hand, it stood as a virtual co-creation arena for students, researchers and company representatives to work together in solving the latter's industrial challenges. The process established the co-creation system as a catalyst for integration of academia in business practices and technical solutions. At the end of a co-creation project, the companies received insight from 'outside sources', ie. young minds from different backgrounds that may be innovative in their approaches to finding Solutions. In addition, if talent was recognized, the companies gained access to potential future employees, as well additional publicity through the student / researcher circles.

In order to ensure process transparency, participation and funding decisions were based on clearly described rules and procedures. All applicants (students and researchers) received adequate feedback on the outcome of the evaluation of their Motivation Letter.

II. INDUSAC Call Conception

The following sections describe the workflow for the co-creation process companies and students/researchers underwent with the support of INDUSAC partners. This workflow starts with issuing a Challenge by a company. The process ends when the company confirms the completion of the co-creation project (the submission of the Solution to the Challenge) including the reporting duties, and researchers and students receive the INDUSAC certificate whereas students also receive funding. The process flow was reassessed during the project's lifetime (using questionnaires for students and researchers and companies) and was subject to modifications.

INDUSAC provided students, researchers and companies with tailored guidance packages to support their co-creation experience based on user journey maps and guidance developed through INDUSAC, as well as a set of Pre-defined Collaborative Approaches (PCAs) which are self-contained project types aimed at providing companies models of project typologies to be adapted to the specific needs of the Challenge being addressed.

Each Challenge was assigned to an INDUSAC Challenge manager. The managers carried out an initial review of Challenges and approved their publication on the platform. In case of a submitted Motivation Letter, a Challenge manager reviewed the Letter and if not rejected, prompted the company to evaluate the Letter. If the Letter was approved by the company, the manager connected the company with the co-creation team with the information about working materials and appropriate deadlines.

2.1 INDUSAC Process Overview

The INDUSAC process involved (i) companies, (ii) students and researchers, and (iii) INDUSAC project partners. For companies, students and researchers, several phases were distinguished (Table 1) and are shown schematically in Figure 1. Separate documents guiding companies and students/researchers are presented in deliverable D1.3 - User Journey Maps and User Guidance (Rudolph et al., 2023b).

Table 1 : Phases of the INDUSAC process and relevant activities for companies and for students/researchers.

	Planning Phase	Onboarding Phase	Search Phase	Project Phase	Offboarding phase
For Companies	identifying a Challenge	registration, posting a Challenge	selection of co-creation teams	assisting students/researchers in solving the Challenge	feedback on the process
For Students / Researchers	raising awareness	/	choosing an appropriate Challenge and assembly of a co-creation team; registration	solving the Challenge	feedback on the process

Figure 1 : Simplified outline of the INDUSAC process.

2.1.1. Timeline of the Co-creation projects

Publication of the call/invitation for universities: May 2023 (already published)

Publication of the call for companies: October 2023 (already published)

Publication of the call for students and researchers: November 2023 (already published)

Cut-off dates for students and researchers to submit Motivation Letters were:
11.02.2024, 18.06.2024, 30.09.2024, 30.10.2024, 30.11.2024, 30.01.2025,
28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025, all at 23:59 CET.

Duration of individual co-creation projects: four to eight weeks.

Timeline for each round:

- Day 0 = cut-off date: deadline for Motivation Letter submission
- Day 0 + 7 days: INDUSAC Challenge managers review the received Motivation Letters and reject those that are not in English, in Latin alphabet
- Day 0 + 21 days: companies make final selections; for rejected Motivation Letters companies use pre-defined justifications
- Day 0 + 25 days: deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (Appendix 6), at which time the co-creation project begins
- Day 0 + 80 days deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams (summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, upskilling questionnaire, testimonial)
- Day 0 + 87 days: companies review the summaries and deliverables
- Day 0 + 126 days: students with approved reports receive funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised)

2.1.1.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

The call initially had three cut-off dates, ie. 31.01.2024, 30.05.2024, and 30.10.2024 (D1.6 – Methodology (M14), Odic et al 2023a). In an attempt to increase the number of co-creation teams, the first cut-off date was extended to 11.02.2024 and the second cut-off date was extended to 18.06.2024. In addition, an additional cut-off date (30.09.2024) was added. Furthermore, piloting was extended with two additional cut-off dates, namely 30.11.2024 and 30.01.2025. Since there was continuous interest from students and room for improvement within the project's duration, the piloting phase was extended further still, to include additional cut-off dates, namely 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025. Note that these updates are not specifically marked in Annex 5 (Call for Students and Researchers) since the Annex reflects the Call in its final form, as it appears on the website.

Previous version of the methodology also included detailed timelines for each cut-off date. For clarity, this has been replaced with a general timeline that was followed regardless of the individual cut-off date.

2.2 Invitation for Universities to Issue Letters of Support

Public universities and public research institutions were invited to join the INDUSAC community by signing a Letter of Support. By providing Letters of Support, universities and research institutions showed their willingness to promote INDUSAC opportunities among their students and researchers.

The aim was to engage with at least 15 organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least 30 at the end of it. The duration of the Open Call for Universities and Research Centres was 18 months, from M9 (May 2023) to M26 (October 2024). The universities and research centres that signed the Letters of Support, received INDUSAC promotional material in order to promote among their students and researchers the participation in the competitions of co-creation teams. Students and researchers were able to express interest, join a co-creation team and submit their Solutions to Challenges any time from M15 (November 2023) till M35 (July 2025).

A list of participating universities and research centres are published on the INDUSAC website.

Students/researchers became aware of INDUSAC through different communication channels - social media (X [Twitter] and YouTube), media relations and promotional materials (such as flyers and rollups at different events). Information about INDUSAC was also available in LinkedIn groups and posts concerning the project, as well as in university press releases or traditional or specialised media (such as articles published by the INDUSAC partners, or scientific publications concerning the project).

The invitation and the Letter of Support are in Annexes 1 and 2.

2.3 Call for Companies

Companies were invited to cooperate in the INDUSAC project by issuing Challenges for students and researchers to solve them within the co-creation teams in four to eight weeks.

The call for companies is in Annex 3.

2.3.1. Registration of Companies on the INDUSAC Platform

Prior to issuing the Challenge, companies registered (signed up) on the platform and provided certain information (Annex 4). The company created a company profile and an account for each company representative. To do this, they created an appropriate user account (company account or company representative account) and filled in all the required information. The mandatory fields were publicly visible on the platform. To successfully register, a company had to accept the terms and conditions outlined in the Call for companies (Annex 3) and the Registration Form (Annex 4).

2.3.2. Issuing a Challenge

The company issued a Challenge to which students/researchers would submit solution proposals, ie. Motivation Letters. A company designated a representative responsible for issuing a Challenge by filling in the PCA template, revising the Challenge if necessary, and ultimately publishing the Challenge.

Companies provided the Challenges based on nine types of Pre-defined Collaboration Approaches (PCAs), which are compiled in the Deliverable D1.2 (Rudolph et al., 2023a). PCAs target nine general areas of potential Challenge: (1) Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, (2) Finding white spots in the product portfolio, (3) Marketing campaign of the future, (4) Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, (5) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), (6) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios), (7) Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, (8) Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and (9) Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system). The PCAs, among other information, included the following:

- title of the Challenge
- description of the problem with additional explanations of key terms
- expectations - what does the company expect in terms of solution, impact and type of collaboration with the co-creation team
- desired co-creation team profile - which skills are desired for solving the Challenge.

To issue a Challenge, a company clicked on "Add Challenge" on the INDUSAC platform. INDUSAC provided nine differently-themed templates to create a Challenge. The templates were designed to guide the company in providing students and researchers, who would be solving the Challenge, with all the information they needed. It was also an opportunity for the company to check that the Challenge had been fully thought through. All Challenges were publicly available and had to include only non-confidential information.

The number of co-creation teams that a company could work with was not limited, but the company ultimately defined the maximum number of co-creation teams that it could work with in the PCA. The company made sure to keep the number of co-creation teams manageable as there would be milestone meetings at which a company representative should be present to make the Challenge a success.

When a company submitted a Challenge it got an automatic notification that the text is being reviewed by the INDUSAC administrators, and the company would be notified about the progress (see Annex 12). Likewise, the company was notified when the Challenge is published.

Company Challenge submissions were a continuous process.

2.3.3. Revision of Issued Challenges

INDUSAC received the company's Challenge and checked it for eligibility. If any information was missing or something was not clear, the company received an email

from the INDUSAC administrators (via the INDUSAC platform) and could revise the Challenge until it was completed.

2.3.4. Publishing of Challenges

Once the revisions were completed (or there were no revisions necessary) and the company confirmed the final version, clicking on the appropriate button changed the status of the Challenge to “published”, and the company received a notification (Annex 12.2).

After the Challenge has been published, the company had the option to host a Challenge presentation. This gave the company the opportunity to have a first meeting with potential co-creation teams interested in their Challenge.

Supporting documents (the library with methods and to-dos developed) was available upon registration.

2.3.5. Update to the previous version of the methodology

An additional cut-off date, 15.03.2025, was added to the original three cut-off dates (December 2023, April 2024, and September 2024) for companies to submit a Challenge. Furthermore, during piloting, a clause was added that if a company would not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter would be nullified and Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time were closed for further applications. This clause was also added to the Call for Students and Researchers. Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 3 (Call for Companies) since the Annex reflects the Call in its final form, as it appears on the website.

2.4 Call for Students and Researchers (financial support to third parties)

2.4.1. Opening the Call

The Call for Students and Researchers opened in November 2023. The INDUSAC project consortium published the open call on the project’s homepage (<https://indusac.eu/>). The call was also published on the Horizon Europe Funding and Tenders portal of the European Commission under the Horizon Europe standards, therefore ensuring transparency, equal treatment, absence of conflict of interest, and confidentiality. All project partners in addition disseminated the call opening via their own dissemination channels. The call was sent also to universities and research organisations that signed INDUSAC letters of support.

The call initially had three cut-off dates, ie. 31.01.2024, 23:59 CET, 30.05.2024, 23:59 CET, and 30.10.2024, 23:59 CET (D1.6 – Methodology (M14), Odic et al 2023a). for a detailed timeline, see Section 2.1.1 and the call text (Annex 5).

2.4.1.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

In an attempt to increase the number of co-creation teams, the first cut-off date was extended to 11.02.2024 and the second cut-off date was extended to 18.06.2024. In addition, an additional cut-off date (30.09.2024) was added. Furthermore, piloting was extended with two additional cut-off dates, namely 30.11.2024 and 30.01.2025. Since there was continuous interest from students and room for improvement within the project's duration, the piloting phase was extended further still, to include additional cut-off dates, namely 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025.

2.4.2. Call for Students and Researchers Section on the INDUSAC Website

There was a dedicated call section for students and researchers on the INDUSAC website (<https://indusac.eu/open-call-for-students-researchers/>) with the full details of the call, supporting documentation such as screenshots of application forms (online available on the INDUSAC platform) and questionnaires, and the FAQ section. Assistance and further information was also available at the email address indusac@ijs.si.

2.4.3. Horizon Europe Funding & Tenders Portal

According to the [European Commission Guidance note](#) on financial support to third parties under Horizon Europe, all calls for third parties and all calls that are implemented by third parties (co-creation teams) must be published on the Funding & Tenders Portal, and on the INDUSAC website. The INDUSAC calls were published on the Funding & Tenders Portal on the following link:

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls/cs/4642?isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502&frameworkProgramme=43108390&order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=100&sortBy=startDate>

and the INDUSAC website (<https://indusac.eu/open-call-for-students-researchers/>).

2.4.4. Registration of students/researchers on the INDUSAC Platform

Prior to submitting Motivation Letters, students and researchers registered (signed up) on the INDUSAC platform (each student/researcher created their own appropriate user account) and provided certain information (Annexes 6 and 7).

Students and researchers complying with the terms and conditions in the Call for students and researchers (Annex 5) were eligible to participate in co-creation projects.

2.4.5. Putting together a Co-creation Team / Matchmaking

A student/researcher selected a Challenge through the INDUSAC website. Clicking on a Challenge provided more information.

Once students/researchers had chosen one (or more) Challenge(s), they could start putting together a co-creation team (which the “matchmaking” refers to). To do so, they could go on the third-party platform Slack (slack.com); using Slack was recommended, but not mandatory. The link to the Slack channel for the concrete Challenge was also visible in the Challenge posting. In this Slack channel, one could express interest and list their skills necessary to solve this Challenge. In this channel, one could also read what other interested parties (students/researchers) had posted. By going through the provided information of every interested person, or engaging in chats, one could start to find a co-creation team.

If students wished to form a co-creation team with others they met on Slack (or elsewhere), they all signed up for the platform individually (if they had not yet done so). If they decided to use Slack, they could create a Slack channel for them as a team themselves where they could start getting to know each other and prepare their Motivation Letter - which is the letter each team has to submit to express their interest in taking on a Challenge. Each co-creation team (created on the platform) automatically got an ID. To submit the Motivation Letter on the platform, the team leader clicked the button to submit a Motivation Letter on the Challenge page. There was a field where the co-creation team leaders could insert all the email addresses of fellow team members (the emails with which their accounts on the platform were created). Each co-creation team member got an email notification where they confirmed participation in a co-creation team and accepted terms and conditions. In case one member did not yet have an account on the platform registered to the email address, they got an invitation to join the platform. Additionally, the team members could also be invited via email by their colleagues or via notification from the platform.

2.4.6. Submission of the Proposal (Motivation Letter)

Once all co-creation team members were registered on the platform, a co-creation team could apply for a Challenge. To do so, the co-creation team needed to submit a common Motivation Letter (ie. a single Motivation Letter per co-creation team, see Annex 8). In this document, a co-creation team had to explain why they are motivated to solve this Challenge, what skills they might have to solve this Challenge, and how it would be addressed. The co-creation team was encouraged to fill in the fields as accurately as possible as these data are important as evaluation criteria (Impact score, Excellence score, Implementation score, and Transversal criteria - see the Call - Annex 5).

Motivation Letters could also outline solutions to the Challenge as well as descriptions of academic and technical ability to provide the solutions if the team already had an idea. It was not necessary to have an idea already at this state. The Motivation Letter form clearly indicated the name of the Challenge, the evaluation fields to fill in, and it also allowed for uploading supporting documents such as CVs, images and video clips.

Motivation Letters needed to be submitted through the platform. Motivation Letters submitted by any other means would not be evaluated.

In the next step, the co-creation team had to select the co-creation team leader. This person would be the one to submit the Motivation Letter (and thus apply for the Challenge). The co-creation team leader would upload the co-creation team's Motivation Letter for the Challenge and add all co-creation team members to the Challenge in the application/Motivation Letter template. To apply, the co-creation team leader accepted the legal terms and conditions and applied for the Challenge. The other members of the co-creation team received notification for joining the co-creation team to submit the Motivation Letter (Annexes 8 and 13.2) and also had to accept the legal terms and conditions. All co-creation team members had to confirm the Motivation Letter through the link in the received notification (Annex 13.3) before the cut-off date.

If there were fields missing, the Motivation Letter could not be submitted and a warning would pop up indicating the specific element of non-compliance (marked with red colour on the registration form). If the co-creation team would not meet the INDUSAC eligibility criteria as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers, verification of which was integrated into the platform's functionalities, they were not able to submit the Motivation Letter.

Motivation Letters could be submitted any time during the open Call. The time recorded by the platform, as submission time of the Motivation Letter, was the official one. Late Motivation Letters were not admitted. After the closing of a cut-off date, no additions or changes to received Motivation Letters were considered. Students and researchers could participate in different co-creation teams (up to three different Motivation Letters to up to three different Challenges).

2.4.6.1 Update to the previous version of the methodology

A student or researcher could not participate in more than one Motivation Letter submitted to the same Challenge.

2.4.7. Acknowledgement of Receipt of Motivation Letter

Upon submission of each Motivation Letter, students/researchers received a notification acknowledging successful submission (Annex 13.3).

2.4.8. Closing the Call

There were several cut-off dates up to which co-creation teams could submit Motivation Letters. The first one was 11.02.2024, as described above. Applications received after 23:59 CET on the respective cut-off day could not be taken into consideration any more, and would be reviewed after the next cut-off date. The last cut-off date (in the previous version of the methodology) was 30.10.2024, after which no applications would be accepted.

2.4.8.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

The new final cut-off date was set to 15.04.2025. With this date the call for the students and researchers was closed.

2.5 Evaluation of Motivation Letters

All Motivation Letters and related data, knowledge and documents were treated in confidence.

The evaluation process included handling the Motivation Letters after the submission and approval or non-approval (rejection) of the received Motivation Letters by the companies.

All students/researchers received adequate feedback on the outcome of the evaluation of their Motivation Letter.

All companies with Challenges got detailed guidelines on the evaluation of Solutions (Annex 11).

2.5.1. Preselection of Motivation Letters

INDUSAC Challenge managers reviewed the received Motivation Letters and rejected those that are not in English and in Latin alphabet.

INDUSAC partners used the platform to send the company the links to the Motivation Letters on the platform for further selection (Annex 12.3).

2.5.2. Evaluation and Feedback from Evaluators (INDUSAC and Company)

The company evaluated (and for justification used pre-prepared explanations) the Motivation Letters through the template (Annex 10) and made final selections based on selection criteria (Annex 10). This evaluation was concluded up to one month after the cut-off date.

In case of rejection, the application process of the respective co-creation teams would stop (and students would not receive financial support).

The co-creation teams received a notification over the INDUSAC platform (Annex 13.4). If the response was positive, the process continued and lead to the initiation of the project.

The evaluation timeline is given in Section 2.1.1. The evaluation form is given in Annex 10.

All co-creation teams were notified about the approval or rejection of their Motivation Letter (Annex 13.4) with justification. In case of approval, students would receive an invitation to sign a FSTP declaration (see the Call for Students and Researchers), and were provided a template (see Call for Students and Researchers). The declaration

needed to be signed by all co-creation student team members. Researchers didn't sign the FSTP declaration.

2.5.2.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

If the company, for any reason (including non-responsiveness or inability to support co-creation projects), would not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter was nullified (and it therefore did not count into the quota of maximum of three Motivation Letters per student) and the Challenge manager from the INDUSAC consortium informed the co-creation team that each team member has the option to participate in another Motivation Letter for a different Challenge. Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time were closed for further applications. Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 5 (Call for Students and Researchers) since the Annex reflects the Call in its final form, as it appears on the website.

The FSTP declaration (Annex 18) has also been slightly updated, to (i) include the co-creation team ID number, (ii) list the full date requirements for six potential student members of the team, (iii) more clearly indicate where the researcher members of the team should be listed, and (iv) indicate signature lines for six potential student members of the team. Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 18 since the Annex reflects the Declaration in its final form, as it is sent out for signing.

2.6 Implementation of Co-creation Projects

Upon signing of the FSTP declaration for a co-creation project by students, the co-creation team and the company were notified with the INDUSAC Challenge manager in cc (Annexes 12.4 and 13.6) and implementation of the co-creation projects could start immediately. A project was not allowed to take longer than eight weeks to finalise.

If the company required any additional contracts to sign (e.g. NDA) with students and researchers, this was arranged outside of the INDUSAC project. For detailed terms and conditions see the Call for students and researchers.

2.6.1. Clarity and Satisfaction Survey for Students / Researchers at the Beginning and at the End of Co-creation Project Implementation

After the co-creation team members received information about approval of their Motivation Letter, they filled out a questionnaire - a brief survey to evaluate their skill level (Annex 14). Questions for students and researchers were intended to provide valuable information on clarity of, and satisfaction with, the co-creation process, in order to be able to improve, if any, methodology elements for the 2nd Call based on the 1st Call, and elements for every subsequent Call based on the previous Call.

2.6.2. Implementation

In the Challenge, a company provided co-creation teams with clear expectations about the co-creation team's skills necessary to carry out the tasks, their expected work results, and a level of the company's involvement. In general, the co-creation teams would work on the Challenge independently of the company, except from regular milestone meetings. In addition to the meetings, the company would be available, within reasonable limits, to answer students'/researchers' questions (through agreed-upon channels, eg. phone, email, Zoom, etc.) regarding their tasks, and to supply further information needed to solve the task. If the students had multiple ideas, the company would assist in steering the co-creation team in the most promising direction; the company also gave insight into ideas that have already been tried in the past and failed. The company's availability for additional assistance (beyond the milestone meetings) was not mandatory, but it was recommended as it was in the interest of obtaining an optimal solution. INDUSAC provided the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams were provided with a planned timeline/mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge (Annex 19). These instructions were customised for each PCA.

Throughout the process, the co-creation teams were expected to have milestone meetings with the company.

The results were reported in a Co-Creation Implementation Report through the INDUSAC platform (Annex 9).

The implementation of the co-creation project took place in several phases: a kick-off meeting between the company and the co-creation team, further (recommended amount between one and three) milestone meetings, and a final meeting, over the course of four to eight weeks. Students/researchers studied the details and methods of the Challenge and investigated the company in more detail. At the kick-off meeting, companies and co-creation teams agreed on the objectives of the co-creation project, and a preferred channel for communicating; companies could inform the co-creation team of their availability for students'/researchers' questions beyond the milestone meetings. Some of this information could be given in the Challenge already and the target deliverables were already defined through the company's chosen PCA. Students/researchers would present a first set of results at the first milestone meeting. Further work would then focus on possible shortcomings and refine the working process accordingly, to ensure that the solution developed in the desired direction. At the final milestone meeting, students/researchers would present a final Solution and receive feedback from the company. The feedback would be incorporated into the students/researchers' deliverables before the final submission.

Below is an example timeline of a co-creation process. The process consisted of a kick-off meeting (KO), followed by up to four project phases with corresponding milestone meetings (MS1, MS2). The milestone meetings were not mandatory, but were highly

recommended. In each project phase, the co-creation teams worked on different tasks in order to prepare the solution. In general, MS1 served for exchanging questions, further details, and feedback on the progress, whereas the penultimate milestone meeting (in this example MS2) was expected to include a presentation of a close-to-ready Solution, to which feedback was given by the company. The process concluded with a final milestone meeting (FM) where the co-creation team presented its results and got the final feedback. The Challenge ended with the submission of the results (in which the final feedback was incorporated) to the company and the company's approval.

Figure 2 : An example timeline of a co-creation process.

2.6.3. Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects

Throughout the process, the company and the co-creation teams may have been approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance. A selection of projects (20-30 during the first six months, and 10 during the last nine months of piloting) was closely monitored by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee in order to identify possible improvements to be implemented on the mechanism.

The selection of the monitored project was based on:

- Geographical distribution
- PCA type distribution
- Date of implementation start

Specific steps in the implementation of the monitoring:

- For monitoring duties, the respective member of the Mentoring Committee would monitor co-creation projects based on a Mentoring plan.
- The INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member established contact with the company and the co-creation team (eg. via email) to check on the progress and verify that the co-creation project was being carried out as agreed at the kick-off meeting.
- The INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member filled out the monitoring plan (the member of the Mentoring Committee checked the status of concrete activity and inserted possible comments).

The Monitoring Report followed the To-Do lists/mentoring plans corresponding to individual PCAs; the Mentoring Committee recorded in the To-Do List the progression of major milestones and any problems that may have occurred, over the co-creation project periods outlined in Figure 2. For each milestone, the Mentoring Committee could check and advise on elements such as clarity of INDUSAC guidelines, adherence to deadlines, timely delivery of results, and communication between the company and the co-creation team.

2.6.3.1 Update to the previous version of the methodology

For clarity, The Monitoring Report structure is shown below. It is structured by filling in the following table (which may be formatted to a landscape layout for convenience):

Company				
Title of Challenge				
Duration of project				
Team members				
Mentoring Committee member(s) (to avoid the need for additional coordination, we suggest a given co-creation project is monitored by an individual committee member; however, you may work in teams if you like)				
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams				
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)				
Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)				
Period*	KO → MS1	MS1 → MS2	MS2 → FM	overall
Clarity of instructions				
Adherence to deadlines				
Delivery of results				
Problems				
Troubleshooting				
Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.				

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

On a more general level, the Monitoring Committee was monitoring the performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and brought to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Apart from interaction with companies/co-creation teams, INDUSAC monitored the efficiency of the platform and user experience (Objective 2) with the aim of:

- *Measuring the up-time of the platform when running aiming for at least 99.9% uptime in a 24/7 regime (INNO).*
- *Measuring less than 1 visit to any Help function for each 10 user sessions logged on the online platform (INNO).*
- *Measuring less than 1 error ticket for 100 user sessions (INNO).*
- *Zero unsolved issues regarding privacy, labour, tax or any other legal framework in the EU (INDUSAC coordinator).*
- *Scoring above 4.0 out of 5 on a Likert scale questionnaire on user experience of the online platform and the offline modalities of the platform (as measurable from the questionnaires) (INDUSAC coordinator).*

2.6.4. Troubleshooting

Conflicts in co-creation projects between companies and students/researchers may arise from miscommunication, mismatched expectations, or technical challenges. In case of conflict between companies and students/researchers from the co-creation project, the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member or INDUSAC coordinator was activated to take the neutral mediation role with structured conflict resolution steps (e.g., hearing both sides, proposing compromises, facilitating negotiation). The issues covered by INDUSAC Mentoring Committee member were formally reported in the monitoring reports. Finding a solution for the conflict at an earlier exit point was prioritised to considering an exit at any of the subsequent exit points.

2.6.5. Exits

In the co-creation process, exit points of companies, students and researchers were foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

In case of an exit where deliverables would be missing, or the solution would not be fulfilling minimal requirements in quality or quantity, financial support to students would not be possible. For details see Annexes 3 and 5 (Call for Companies and Call for Students and Researchers).

2.6.6. Reporting

2.6.6.1. Reporting by students and researchers

Once the co-creation project implementation was completed, the co-creation team submitted an implementation report (see the Call for students and researchers).

The implementation report included:

- Deliverables (according to a specific PCA) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the Challenge.
- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 15) - filled out by each member of the co-creation team
 - Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
 - Compliance with the ethics requirement

As per the [Horizon Europe Work Programme](#), selected outcomes of the calls were published without delay, including a description of third-party projects, the date of the award, the duration, and the legal name and country of the students/researchers.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

(Annex 15; comparing answers to these questions before the start of project and after its completion provided a satisfaction score, as set out in Objective 1 of the INDUSAC project, aiming for a minimum average satisfaction score of 3.8 out of 5)

Some of the questions in the questionnaire provided data for checking the level of achievement of Objectives 5 and 7:

- *Demonstration of the feasibility of running the IAC mechanism with less than 3,000 EUR per co-creation team.*
- *At least 70% of students and researchers participating reporting at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC.*
- *At least 70% of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the programme as being suitable).*
- *At least 80% of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a programme to their peers.*
- *An improved set of skills in students and researchers by at least 30% compared to before the beginning of the project, allowing them to rapidly expand their skill set in*

a short period of time and to find themselves more prepared for the business environment.

2.6.6.2. Reporting by companies

The company provided feedback on the INDUSAC process through the INDUSAC platform that included:

- Deliverable quality assessment (which was submitted by the co-creation team - for details see 2.6.7; Annex 11)
- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 16)
 - Questionnaire
 - Testimonial

The company could choose to write a letter of recommendation for the co-creation team members.

2.6.6.2.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

Due to a KPI (*At least 80% of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a program to their peers*) in the project’s Objective 5, a question was added on how likely a company is to recommend participation in this type of programme to its peers (Annex 16). Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 16 since the Annex reflects the questionnaire in its final form, as it appears online.

2.6.7. Evaluation of Solutions

The company evaluated the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which was given automatically if the Solution was submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

The Evaluation Board reviewed the rejected Solutions, if any, of the Challenge proposed by the co-creation teams (according to the criteria in the Calls) that gave the final score of each co-creation project and a list of FSTP student recipients (Annex 11).

The Evaluation Board was composed by work package leaders. It was coordinated by JSI and the composition could be extended by inviting External Evaluators, selected from the companies on ad-hoc basis and the Ethics experts from the Inclusiveness Board, if needed.

After this step, administrative procedure with students began in order for them to receive payment from INDUSAC to the bank account they indicated during the project initiation. Students and researchers would receive a certificate of participation from INDUSAC.

2.6.7.1 Update to the previous version of the methodology

Questions from the form for evaluating Solutions (Annex 11) as well as the request to provide a short description of the project results, were incorporated into the questionnaire for companies after completion of the co-creation project (Annex 16). Note that this update is not specifically marked in Annex 16 since the Annex reflects the questionnaire in its final form, as it appears online

2.6.8. Financial Support for Students

A dedicated budget of financial support to third parties (FSTP) was available in a total amount of 900,000 EUR as a lump sum. The total amount per co-creation team for student members of the co-creation team was 3,000 EUR gross, out of which up to 1,000 EUR gross per student member. The amount would be transferred as a lump sum to the student after the solution for the Challenge is confirmed by the Evaluation Team.

Only students within the co-creation teams received financial support (FSTP). Neither researchers nor companies would receive FSTP.

All FSTP payments to the students were done by the INDUSAC coordinator. The INDUSAC coordinator oversaw and monitored the FSTP towards students based on the FSTP declarations signed once co-creation teams were selected. Nine cut-off dates for payments were set up (no later than 30 days after the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised). The amount was in no case higher than 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team (i.e. 1,000 EUR gross per student as a lump sum). A single student/researcher would be able to participate in more than one team (at the team assembly step) but up to three submitted Motivation Letters. A single student received up to 1,000 EUR gross for each co-creation project and was limited up to 3,000 EUR gross if the student participated in three co-creation projects.

Taxation

Payments were done by the Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia). Since Jožef Stefan Institute was transferring financial support to third parties (FSTP) to natural persons (individuals - students), Slovenian legislation and Slovenian accounting standards had to be followed. The rate of taxation varies from country to country; in Slovenia it is 25%.

2.6.8.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

In agreement with the nine cut-off dates for submission of Motivation Letters, nine (instead of three) cut-off dates for FSTP payments were set up. Furthermore, it was taken into account that a student or researcher could not participate in more than one Motivation Letter submitted to the same Challenge (see Section 2.4.6.1).

The FSTP funds that the students received as part of the INDUSAC project had to be, like all taxable income, reported by the recipient to the competent office of the Financial Administration of the country of their residency so that the FSTP funds could be taxed accordingly.

2.7 Follow-up on Co-creation Projects

2.7.1. Follow-up Challenges

If a company published a Challenge before the first cut-off date, it could create a follow-up Challenge for a subsequent cut-off date. This could be, for example, a continuation of the Challenge based on the last Solution.

For a timeline see Section 2.1.1.

III. Definitions and Roles of INDUSAC Boards and Committees within Co-creation Process

3.1 INDUSAC Evaluation Board

The Evaluation Board reviewed the rejected Solutions of the Challenge proposed by the co-creation teams (according to the criteria in the Calls) and gave the final score of each co-creation project and a list of FSTP student recipients. The list of rejected Solutions was prepared by the INDUSAC coordinator and sent to the Evaluation Board.

Function: Committee responsible for validating the projects performance in the Selection, Monitoring and Evaluation in T3.3.

The Evaluation Board members attended meetings as needed. Evaluation Board members communicated with each other regularly via emails.

3.1.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

The Evaluation Board was in charge of carrying out the analysis of the satisfaction / clarity / upskilling questionnaires (filled out by co-creation team members and companies) and preparation of D3.5: Monitoring and evaluation report. The Board also checked the quality of projects, with an assessment that was used for improving the mechanisms.

The Evaluation Board was composed of work package leaders. It was coordinated by JSI and the composition could be extended by inviting External Evaluators, selected from the companies on an ad-hoc basis and the Ethics experts from the Inclusiveness Board, if needed.

3.2 INDUSAC Evaluation Team

The Evaluation Team was composed of the Evaluation Board (one INDUSAC member) and a company representative, both of which were included in the evaluation for a particular case/Challenge/Solution.

3.3 Inclusiveness Board

The Inclusiveness Board was composed of appointed partner representatives and coordinated by the INDUSAC coordinator.

Function: the board was responsible for verification of inclusiveness, gender equality, and other ethical issues.

3.4 Mentoring Committee

The Mentoring Committee was composed of appointed INDUSAC partner representatives and coordinated by the INDUSAC coordinator.

Function: the committee was in charge of monitoring the performance and quality of selected co-creation projects (20-30 for the first 6 months, and 10 for the following months) in order to identify improvements on the INDUSAC methodology / platform.

3.4.1. Update to the previous version of the methodology

The Mentoring Committee was in charge of carrying out a quick monitoring of the performance of projects. It was also in charge of preparation of the in-depth monitoring report (D3.4) on selected co-creation projects with the aim of updating the INDUSAC Methodology (D1.6).

The Mentoring Committee was composed of WP3 participants, ad-hoc companies and coordinated by JSI. In some cases, ethics experts could be invited, if needed.

IV. INDUSAC's human-centred approach on the co-creation process

INDUSAC's co-creation process involved individuals from different backgrounds that came together to collaboratively create and innovate. In such processes, prioritising human-centred aspects becomes essential to ensure the process is inclusive, ethical and meaningful for students, researchers and companies, as well as for the European society. INDUSAC, through its methodology, considered several aspects to ensure the appropriate human-centred approach, including gender dimension and social sciences and humanities integration.

- **Inclusivity:** INDUSAC's gender and geographical balance requirements ensured diversity and representation among the participants, encouraging participants from different genders, ethnicities, and backgrounds. The Inclusiveness Board ensured an inclusive environment where participants feel respected and empowered to contribute with their unique perspectives.
- **Gender dimension:** The support material, specifically designed for each PCA, provided guidance to address specific needs, and perspectives of individuals of different genders. Gender-sensitive research methods, such as gender-disaggregated data collection or gender-focused interviews, could be employed to gather insights and inform the co-creation process. INDUSAC's team formation requirements ensured gender balance by promoting diverse gender representation. The INDUSAC Inclusiveness Board was responsible for creating a safe and respectful environment for open dialogue and valuing gender-specific insights.
- **Interdisciplinarity:** INDUSAC team creation process involved participants from a wide range of disciplines, including social sciences and humanities. Incorporating diverse perspectives, fostering holistic problem-solving, and generating innovative solutions that consider both the human element and the broader societal implications.
- **User Perspective:** PCAs were designed to place the end-users at the center of the co-creation process. Support material provided tools to understand their needs, desires, and pain points through research methods.
- **Collaboration:** INDUSAC mechanism was based on collaboration, cooperation, and co-learning among participants. Each PCA, in which challenges are based, proposed a process timeline and a to-do list (Mentoring plan), designed to promote the culture of sharing knowledge, skills, and experiences. Support material included activities that foster mutual understanding and learning.
- **Iterative feedback:** PCA's proposed process timeline incorporated at least three feedback sessions between students/researchers and company representatives throughout the co-creation process. This methodology encouraged participants to provide constructive criticism, suggestions, and insights at various stages.

Iterations and refinement of ideas based on the feedback received ensured continuous improvement and successful outcomes.

- Ethical considerations: INDUSAC upheld the highest ethical standards and ensured responsible practices throughout the co-creation process as described in the Call for companies and the Call for students and researchers. The INDUSAC mechanism respected privacy, confidentiality, and consent and considered the ethical implications of any data collected and used.

V. FINAL REMARKS

While the INDUSAC consortium made sure to include clear instructions for navigating the project, and clear eligibility conditions for participating, at appropriate points, such as the INDUSAC website and platform, wide dissemination and engagement with companies and co-creation teams for assistance was necessary for successful matchmaking. INDUSAC partners therefore share the understanding that the methodology and its elements described in the previous sections represented a coherent workflow, and committed to supporting students, researchers, companies, and each other, in successful piloting.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable represents one of the two major pillars of the INDUSAC project, namely, the project's methodology. As such, it contains all the operational elements necessary for the execution of the project – the phases, steps, definitions, and supporting documentation for the open calls within the project. In its final updated form it represents a basis for similar future projects, particularly in terms of timelines and management of financially supported co-creation projects carried out by students, researchers, and companies.

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VIII. TABLE OF CHANGES TO THE PREVIOUS VERSION

page 2	updated History of Changes
page 11	it is pointed out that certain suggestions by students, researchers, and companies, which were collected by the Mentoring Committee, were implemented during the project but did not change the workflow or had a major impact on methodology
pages 11-13	aims of the project are listed in detail to accurately reflect the Grant Agreement
pages 17, 18, 25, 61	the first two cut-off dates for students to submit Motivation Letters were extended, and additional cut-off dates were added resulting in nine cut-off dates in total, with the final cut-off date set to 15.04.2025
page 18	for clarity, detailed timelines for individual co-creation project rounds were replaced with a general timeline that was followed for each cut-off date
pages 24, 33	a rule was added to the Call for Students and Researchers that a student or researcher could not participate in more than one Motivation Letter submitted to the same Challenge
pages 21, 49, 54	fourth cut-off date for companies to submit Challenges (15.03.2025) was added to the Call for Companies
pages 21, 26, 52, 65	a rule was added to the Call for Companies and the Call for Students and Researchers that if the company, for any reason (including non-responsiveness or inability to support co-creation projects), would not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter would be nullified (and therefore would not count into the quota of maximum of three Motivation Letters per student) and each team member would have the option to participate in another Motivation Letter for a different Challenge. Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time were closed for further applications.
page 26	The FSTP declaration (Annex 18) has also been slightly updated, to (i) include the co-creation team ID number, (ii) list the full date requirements for six potential student members of the team, (iii) more clearly indicate where the researcher members of the team should be listed, and (iv) indicate signature lines for six potential student members of the team.
page 29	to illustrate the process more clearly, structure of the Monitoring Report is added to this document
pages 33, 67	the taxation procedure was simplified
pages 35, 36	Structure and roles of the Evaluation Board and the Mentoring Committee were slightly redefined while maintaining the core idea of their function
page 101	questions from the form for evaluation of Solutions were added to the Questionnaire for companies after completion of the co-creation project

page 104

a question was added to the Questionnaire for companies after completion of the co-creation project asking for a short description of the project results, and probability of recommendation of participation in this kind of project to the company's peers

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ANNEX 1 : Call for Universities on the INDUSAC Website

Public universities are invited to promote the INDUSAC project among their students via the INDUSAC web page: <https://indusac.eu/invitation-to-participate-in-an-exciting-new-project-aimed-at-strengthening-the-collaboration-between-industry-and-academia/>

The Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate an Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism.

Within the project, the INDUSAC project partners will facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows the development of solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries^[1].

Students and researchers will create international co-creation teams of at least three members that will solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks. INDUSAC has a budget of 900,000 EUR gross intended for student members of co-creation teams, where mini-grants of 3,000 EUR gross will be distributed among student members of each co-creation team (ie. up to 1,000 EUR gross per student). By solving companies' Challenges, students will get international working experiences, collaborative experiences by working with students and researchers from different countries, and transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results orientation, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, and analytical thinking, among others), access to companies from the EU and associated countries, references, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC. By participating in co-creation teams, researchers will gain companies' and students' contacts, letters of recommendation from industry partners, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC.

In support of this project, we would kindly ask your organisation to sign the attached Letter of Support. This letter will show your willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities among your students and researchers and will serve as a foundation for future collaboration.

If you agree to sign the attached Letter of Support, please add the official letterhead/logo of your organisation and send it back to us, together with the logo of your organisation.

Your logo will be displayed on the project's website (www.indusac.eu) among the logos of the other supporting organisations.

INDUSAC partners will provide you with all the necessary promo materials (mostly e-format) about INDUSAC opportunities that you can distribute among your students and researchers.

No financial obligations shall take place.

We would be honoured to gain your organisation's support for this project, and we would be happy to provide you with more information about the project and its goals. If you are interested in learning more, please do not hesitate to contact us at indusac@ijs.si.

ANNEX 2 : Letter of Support by Universities**LETTER OF SUPPORT**

Place, date: _____

To: Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

With this letter, we would like to express the support of our organisation,
_____ (*insert the organisation name*), for the
HORIZON EUROPE project “INDUSAC” (INDUSAC has received funding from the European
Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101070297).

We confirm our willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities among our students
and researchers.

We are looking forward to future collaboration.

*Name of Legal Representative (eg. Rector/Director)*_____
Signature and stamp

ANNEX 3 : Call for Companies

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR COMPANIES

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project [INDUSAC](#) under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (4-8-week) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support in the form of financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome: 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia.

Companies are invited to provide Challenges to receive Solutions from the co-creation teams (students and researchers) within four to eight weeks after the selection process of teams is finished.

Opening date: October 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, four cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Challenge: Companies issue Challenges continuously from the call opening date up to one of four cut-off dates:

- 15.12.2023, 23:59 CET
- 15.04.2024, 23:59 CET
- 15.11.2024, 23:59 CET
- 15.03.2025, 23:59 CET

Eligibility

Country: Companies established in the EU as well as companies established in associated countries will be eligible to issue Challenges: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, Morocco, UK. Companies with headquarters outside of listed countries but with branch offices and subsidiaries established in countries listed above, are also eligible.

Company type: entities considered as companies according to the Wikipedia source (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_legal_entity_types_by_country) are eligible to submit

Challenges. There are no restrictions on the sector or size of a company to issue a Challenge (startups and large enterprises may apply as well as SMEs).

Language: English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration on the INDUSAC Platform

The registration process (Annex 4) allows a company to create a profile and publish a Challenge on the INDUSAC platform. During the registration, the company is invited to provide certain information about the company, and verify that a company accepts the terms and conditions of this Call.

Step 2 - Issuing a Challenge on the INDUSAC Platform

On the INDUSAC platform, the company selects from nine different Challenge templates: (1) Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, (2) Finding white spots in the product portfolio, (3) Marketing campaign of the future, (4) Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, (5) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), (6) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios), (7) Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, (8) Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and (9) Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system).. The Challenge templates - among other information - ask for the following:

- title of the Challenge,
- description of the problem with additional explanations of key terms,
- expectations - what does the company expect in terms of solution, impact and type of collaboration with the co-creation team,
- desired co-creation team profile - which skills are desired in solving the Challenge,
- the maximum number of co-creation teams that the company can work with,

Challenges, together with the company's name, county and website will be publicly available and have to include only non-confidential information.

Once Challenges are published, students and researchers can apply, until the corresponding cut-off dates for submitting Motivation Letters (see Call for Students and Researchers), to solve them. Companies will be eligible for receiving possible solutions to their Challenges within 4-8 weeks after they approve the submitted Motivation Letters.

Step 3 - Selection of co-creation teams

Within this step the company selects the most suitable co-creation teams through selection of their Motivation Letter. Motivation Letters will be evaluated based on Team's motivation, Excellence score, Impact score, Team and resources, and Transversal criteria (Table 2).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?

- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the four-to-eight-week time frame?

(5). TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 2 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5 %	5	0,25
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5
Impact	30 %	5	1,5
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores. A ranking list will be prepared. INDUSAC will provide companies with pre-defined justifications for rejecting Motivation Letters.

If the company, for any reason (including non-responsiveness or inability to support co-creation projects), does not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter is nullified (and it therefore does not count into the quota of maximum of three Motivation Letters per student) and the Challenge manager from the INDUSAC consortium informs the co-creation team that each team member has the option to participate in another Motivation Letter for a different Challenge. Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time are closed for further applications.

Step 4 - Implementation of co-creation projects

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge. These instructions will be customised for each Challenge type.

Throughout the process, the company should have a kick-off meeting, at least one (highly recommended between one and three) milestone meeting and a final meeting with each co-creation team. In addition to the meetings, the company will be available, within reasonable limits, to answer students'/researchers' questions (through agreed-upon channels, eg. phone, email, Zoom, the INDUSAC platform chat, etc.) regarding their tasks, and to supply further information needed to solve the task. If the students have multiple ideas, the company will assist in steering the co-creation team in the most promising direction; the company will also give insight into ideas that have already been tried in the past and failed. The company's availability for additional assistance (beyond the milestone meetings) is not mandatory, but it is recommended as it is in the interest of obtaining an optimal solution.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process, the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 5 - Reporting

The company provides feedback on the INDUSAC process (Annex 11 and 16) that will include:

- Deliverable quality assessment of the Solution submitted by the co-creation team

The company evaluates the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution. The deliverable quality assessment (Evaluation of Solutions) will be submitted via the platform.

- Questionnaire “after” (Annex 16)
 - Questionnaire
 - Testimonial

The questionnaire “after” will be provided by a third party provider (<https://1ka.arnes.si>) and questionnaire data will be collected and analyzed by INDUSAC partners outside of the platform.

Timeline

For receiving Motivation Letters in February 2024 and Solutions in May 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 15.12.2023, 23:59 CET (first cut-off date) so as to have them published by 31.12.2023.

For receiving Motivation Letters in June 2024 and Solutions in September 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 15.04.2024, 23:59 CET (second cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.04.2024.

For receiving Motivation Letters in November 2024 and Solutions in February 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 15.11.2024, 23:59 CET (third cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.11.2024.

For receiving Motivation Letters in January 2025 or later, and Solutions in April 2025 or later (but not later than July 2025), companies need to submit Challenges by 15.03.2025, 23:59 CET (fourth cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.03.2025.

Terms and Conditions for companies

Number of Challenges issued

A company may issue more than one Challenge.

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities)

The company confirms that it is not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The company confirms that it is not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

The company confirms that the text, data and other content of the Challenges is non-confidential.

For cases where companies wish to share with the selected co-creation teams its confidential information, they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the co-creation team before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-Disclosure of Information and Impartiality (Annex 17) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

The company confirms that the material shared by the company representatives is owned by the company they represent and / or they have acquired the rights for their usage.

Should the cooperation between students/researchers and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties (company, co-creation team) agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.
- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Long-term relevance of Challenges

For all issued Challenges, the companies acknowledge that Motivation Letters will be evaluated at nine cut-off dates and that their Challenge, regardless of how soon it was issued, must still be relevant for the first upcoming cut-off date.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance ([European Commission, 2021](#)) the company must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human foetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

The company may decide to reject a proposed Motivation Letter. The company assures that any rejections of Motivation Letters will be based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters (following the INDUSAC evaluation criteria) and not be affected by the co-creation teams' gender or citizenship/residency.

If a co-creation team has provided draft Solutions or Solution proposals in applying to a Challenge, but ends up rejected, the company commits to discarding the rejected proposal without any further use of the solutions proposed therein.

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

The company must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

The company confirms that it is not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with the company and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Solutions.

Disputes and exits

The parties (companies, students and researchers) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute.

In the co-creation process exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The company acknowledges that it can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The company can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC

and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

ANNEX 4 : Registration Form for Companies

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for companies

Marked with ** for data that will be visible on the public part of the platform without the login

- **Name of the company
- Address of the company
- **Country (drop down menu of eligible countries: all EU countries and all Associated countries)
- VAT number
- ID number
- Name of legal representative
- E-mail of legal representative (organisation email is mandatory)
- **Website
- Name of contact person
- E-mail of contact person
- **Contact phone number
- Nr. of employees (tick suitable box: 0-10, 11-50, 50-250, 250-1,000, more than 1,000) also for statistical purposes
- [NACE code](#) (for statistical purposes): A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B - Mining and quarrying, C - Manufacturing, D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, E - Water supply; sewerage; waste management and remediation activities, F - Construction, G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, H - Transporting and storage, I - Accommodation and food service activities, J - Information and communication, K - Financial and insurance activities, L - Real estate activities, M - Professional, scientific and technical activities, N - Administrative and support service activities, O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security, P - Education, Q - Human health and social work activities, R - Arts, entertainment and recreation, S - Other services activities, T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods - and services - producing activities of households for own use, U - Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.

- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Companies
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (company data, such as specific contacts, to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published)

ANNEX 5 : Call for Students and Researchers

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project [INDUSAC](#) under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (4-8-week) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome:

- 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia,
- Supported co-creation projects shall include at least 50% female representation overall (not on the individual co-creation project level).
- 60% members of the co-creation teams must be from Widening Countries.
- Distribution of 900.000 EUR gross for FSTP to student members of the co-creation teams,

Students and researchers are invited to create co-creation teams and solve companies' Challenges within 4-8 weeks.

Opening date: November 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, multiple cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Motivation Letter:

- 11.02.2024, 23:59 CET
- 18.06.2024, 23:59 CET
- 30.09.2024, 23:59 CET
- 30.10.2024, 23:59 CET
- 30.11.2024, 23:59 CET
- 30.01.2025, 23:59 CET
- 28.02.2025, 23:59 CET
- 31.03.2025, 23:59 CET
- 15.04.2025, 23:59 CET

The Motivation Letter from a co-creation team is considered submitted once all co-creation team members confirm participation in the co-creation team and confirm the terms and conditions.

Eligibility

Eligible countries: In accordance with the [Horizon Europe Call](#), students and researchers in each co-creation team must come from EU Member States (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden), in particular Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; [source](#)) or Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Iceland, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. Morocco, 18. UK), **as indicated by their citizenship or residency.**

Eligibility for Students.

- Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual student will be able to participate in a maximum of three submitted Motivation Letters.

Eligibility for Researchers.

- Researchers must be employed at a public research organisation during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual researcher will be able to participate in a maximum of three submitted Motivation Letters.

Eligibility of Co-creation Teams

- The co-creation team must have at least three and up to six members.
- Co-creation team members must be from at least three different EU Member States or Associated Countries.
- The co-creation team has to be gender balanced (operationally, including at least two different gender options (Male, Female, Would rather not say) in the team).
- Each co-creation team must include at least one student, ie. no co-creation team may comprise exclusively researchers.

English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Budget: up to 1,000 EUR gross per student (lump sum), up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team wherein only students are eligible for funding; 900,000 EUR gross in total, for supporting 300 projects.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration

Prior to submitting Motivation Letters, students and researchers register (sign-up) (Annexes 6 and 7) on the INDUSAC platform (each student/researcher creates their own appropriate user account) and provides certain information.

Step 2 - Putting together a co-creation team

A student/researcher selects a Challenge. Once students/researchers have chosen a Challenge, they start putting together a co-creation team. Each co-creation team (created on the platform) automatically gets an ID. They may use the platform Slack (slack.com) or another communication channel of their choice.

Students already registered on the INDUSAC platform can invite students not yet registered, to join a co-creation team via e-mail. Once a co-creation team has been assembled, members can create their own channels and discuss their ambitions, goals, and further details. In this chat, they also start preparing their Motivation Letter.

Step 3 - Motivation Letter submission

Once all co-creation team members are registered on the platform, a co-creation team can apply for a Challenge. The co-creation team must select the co-creation team leader, who submits a common Motivation Letter (ie. a single Motivation Letter per co-creation team) that is confirmed by all co-creation team members before the final submission.

After the closing of a cut-off date, no additions or changes to received Motivation Letters will be considered.

Motivation Letters (Annex 8) need to be submitted through the INDUSAC platform. Motivation Letters submitted by any other means will not be evaluated.

After the cut-off date the company selects co-creation teams based on evaluation criteria and instructions for Motivation letter (Annex 8, Table 3).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)

- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5). TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 3 : Evaluation criteria and scoring system for Motivation Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5 %	5	0,25
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5
Impact	30 %	5	1,5
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

If the company, for any reason (including non-responsiveness or inability to support co-creation projects), does not provide a decision on a submitted Motivation Letter within three weeks after the cut-off date for submitting Motivation Letters, the Motivation Letter is nullified (and it therefore does not count into the quota of maximum of three Motivation Letters per student) and the Challenge manager from the INDUSAC consortium informs the co-creation team that each team member has the option to participate in another Motivation Letter for a different Challenge. Challenges of companies that did not review submitted Motivation Letters on time are closed for further applications.

Step 4 - Before the start of the co-creation project implementation

Students

Once the co-creation project is approved each student member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (Annex 14), provides certain data (bank details, etc) and signs the FTSP declaration electronically.

Researchers

Once the co-creation project is approved, each research member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (Annex 14).

Step 5 - Implementation of co-creation projects

Students and researchers must solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks.

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge.

Throughout the process, each co-creation team should have the kick-off, at least one milestone meeting, and the feedback meeting with the company.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 6 - Reporting

The results are reported in a Co-Creation Implementation Report through the INDUSAC platform (Annex 9) latest 8 weeks after the start of the project.

The implementation report will include:

- Deliverables (according to a specific Challenge type) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the Challenge.
- Questionnaire “after” - filled out by each member of the co-creation team
 - Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
 - Compliance with the ethics requirement

The implementation report will be submitted via the platform. The questionnaire “after” will be provided by a third party provider (<https://1ka.arnes.si>) and questionnaire data will be collected and analyzed by INDUSAC partners outside of the platform.

Evaluation of Solutions

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 10 and the weight of each one of these criteria, in the final score, will be as follows: Deliverable quality of submitted Solution (30% of the overall score); Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the

overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Timeline

- Day 0: deadline for Motivation Letter submission
- Day 0 + 25 days: deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (Appendix 6), at which time the co-creation project begins
- Day 0 + 80 days deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams
- Day 0 + 126 days: students with approved reports receive funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised)

Financial support to third parties

Financial support to third parties (FSTP) based on a Lump sum is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams up to 1,000 EUR gross per student.

Students receive financial support to third parties after approval of the Implementation report on a Solution (as described in Step 6 - Reporting of this Call).

INDUSAC coordinator shall transfer the funds to students within thirty (30) days from the date of the approval of the implementation report (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised) on a Solution / final confirmation from the INDUSAC Evaluation Board.

Taxation

Payments will be done by the Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia). Since Jožef Stefan Institute will be transferring financial support to third parties (FSTP) to natural persons (individuals - students), Slovenian legislation and Slovenian accounting standards must be followed. The rate of taxation varies from country to country; in Slovenia it is 25%.

The FSTP funds that the students receive as part of the INDUSAC project must be, like all taxable income, reported by the recipient to the competent office of the Financial Administration of the country of their residency so that the FSTP funds can be taxed accordingly. In case of questions, the students are advised to consult the financial administration of the country of their residency about further steps.

Terms and Conditions for students and researchers

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities). The students/researchers confirm that they are not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The students / researchers confirm that they are not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

For cases where students/researchers wish to share with the selected company their confidential information they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the company before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality (Annex 17) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

Should the cooperation between student/researcher and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their

economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.

- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance (European Commission, 2021) the co-creation team must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human foetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

Students/researchers must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

By applying for the Call, students and researchers confirm that neither they nor their close family ties (spouse, domestic or non-domestic partner, child, sibling, parent etc.) are in business or scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the company behind the challenge they are submitting the Motivation Letter for.

Students further confirm that they are not receiving double financing for any of their activities within the INDUSAC project, ie. challenge solving activities within the co-creation team will not be funded from other sources except the INDUSAC financial support for third parties.

Applicants receiving financial support cannot be affiliated to any of the consortium partners, for example as consortium partner's board members or employees, with the exception of students employed for performing services unrelated to the challenge.

Disputes and exits

The parties (students, researchers, companies) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute.

In the co-creation process exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The students/researchers acknowledge that they can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The students/researchers can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Promotion. The members of the co-creation teams agree to provide statements / testimonials / experiences that can be published on the project website together with parts of the Challenge, through INDUSAC media and in project partners media.

Co-creation teams are given an option to have the INDUSAC communication team prepare a success story / a good practice story based on the co-creation team's project and results.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

ANNEX 6 : Registration form for Students

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for students

Data needed when a student/researcher creates an account (**some of the data is automatically inserted in the template for the FSTP Declaration that the students sign with INDUSAC**):

Mandatory fields marked with * are for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform

- Name*
- Family name*
- Address
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries) *
- Gender (tick: Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail
- Month / year of study start – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Foreseen month and year of study end (Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed) – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Name of public university where you study *
- Country of the university *
- Website of the university
- Mark your area of study:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)

- Physics (PHY)
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

ANNEX 7 : Registration Form for Researchers

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for researchers

Marked with * for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform

- Name *
- Family name *
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries)*
- Gender (tick Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail (organisation email is mandatory)
- Name of public research organisation where you work *
- Website of their employer *
- Mark your area of research:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)
 - Physics (PHY)
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

ANNEX 8 : Motivation Letter Form

Challenge title

Attachments

*Drag and drop your files here –
Add pictures and other visuals to increase the description of your solution proposal*

Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution. Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS

Team ID

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

Describe your team motivation

Describe your team motivation in your own words. You should include why you as a team are most suitable to find a great solution for this challenge in collaboration with the industry partner. You can use this field to give a quick introduction to all the team members and let everybody state their personal motivation for this challenge. The conclusion should answer why you as a team are well prepared to solve this challenge.

Example Conclusion: We as a team will find a great solution together since we not only come from different countries but we also study three very different degrees which will help us to think out of the box. Jane studies mechanical engineering and has a lot of experience with building physical prototypes. Tim is in his third year of an architecture bachelor's. He knows a lot about different materials, and has also been building prototypes since his first semester. Melanie studies corporate law and works in her free time for an NGO. We see ourselves as qualified not only to find an innovative solution but also to visualize it through a prototype. Furthermore, we will focus on finding a sustainable and durable solution that can be used in all countries. To make sure it fits

with the different countries' regulations, Melanie uses her knowledge from a European corporate law class

How will you address the following aspects? (you may respond to all the criteria if possible) (up to 5000 characters):

Excellence

How will your team reach an excellent solution for this challenge? Why is your team one that can propose a solution that might become a real innovation?

Impact

Why do you believe your team will find a solution that can be successful on the market? To what level will your solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? You may also describe what you already found out about the companies' competition and how you are trying to get to a differentiated solution. Do you already have ideas about how a solution to this challenge might not only solve the challenge but tackle a respective structural problem? How important will the project in your opinion be for the company? Will the solution be implementable also in other sectors?

Team & Resources

Demonstrate your transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, your ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and your capacity to carry through your ideas and understand the dynamics of the market you are trying to tap into. Do you have specific resources that qualify you as a team specifically to find an excellent solution? Do you plan a visit to the companies' premises within the duration of the project? Do you plan any other travel (national or international; e.g., visiting a library, visiting a teammate, visiting a prototyping centre etc.)? How much time (hours/team member) do you plan to invest in this project?

Transversal criteria

Do you have ideas to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within your way to a solution for the challenge? If yes you may describe here how or why you are planning to do so.

Idea for solution (optional)

Optional: If you already have an idea for a solution for this challenge, please briefly describe it here. Note: filling this field is optional (up to 5000 characters)

Describe the idea you have for solving this challenge as clearly as you can. It might include which technology you plan on using, procedures you believe solve the challenge, services or other details you came already up with in your team. If applicable please make sure you are not disclosing any confidential information.

About you

ANNEX 9 : Template for Co-creation Implementation Report

To be filled out by each member of the co-creation team.

Co-Creation Implementation Report	
Title of the Challenge	
Team Leader	
Team Member	
Team Member	
Start of project	(date)
End of project	(date)
<p>Short description of the project results. Please provide a short description of the project results and a short description of your personal contribution (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include classified information.</p>	
<p>List of Deliverables prepared and uploaded on the platform</p>	
<p>Inclusiveness statement (explain in a few sentences how your solution is inclusive, ie. not excluding any groups of individuals in terms of gender, race, nationality, etc.)</p>	

Upskilling, clarity and satisfaction questionnaire	Annex 14
<p>Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:</p> <p><i>“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”</i></p> <p><i>“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience.”</i></p>	

ANNEX 10 : Template for Evaluation: Motivation Letters

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 4 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivaton Letters.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score
Team's Motivation	5 %	5	0,25	
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5	
Impact	30 %	5	1,5	
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5	
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25	
Total	100 %	25	5	

Scoring system with scores 0 to 5 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - Motivation Letter makes no effort to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1 - Motivation Letter does not address all aspects or covers all aspects poorly
- 2 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects but at least half of them poorly
- 3 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 4 - All aspects clearly presented but could be improved
- 5 - All aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Motivation, 2 Excellence, 3 Impact, 4 Team and Resources, 5 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Decision (accept / reject): _____

Justification in case of rejection (select one or more options)

- The teams' motivation is not convincing enough and several parts are poorly addressed.
- Excellence: The foreseen approach, the credibility of the proposed methodology and the efficiency and quality of the proposed work are not convincing.
- Impact: The motivation letter does not provide information relevant or credible enough to consider that the team will be able to provide a differentiated or innovative solution that can be successful on the market or relevant for the company.
- Team and resources: One or several of the required aspects, within the team and resources, to develop a solution in four to eight weeks time frame are missing. Transversal criteria: The ideas on how to include transversal criteria within the teams' way to a solution for the challenge are poorly considered.

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.

- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5). TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

ANNEX 11 : Template for Evaluation of Solutions

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 5 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Solutions.

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score	Evaluator
Deliverable quality	30 %	10	3		company
Business performance indicators / Technical performance indicators	60 %	10	6		company
Deadline compliance	10 %	10	1		points given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time
Total	100 %	30	10		

Scoring system with scores 0 to 10 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly
- 3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly

5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved

7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved

9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

- Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Decision: _____

Justification for the company to describe the deliverable quality (select one option)

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

ANNEX 12 : Notifications that Companies Receive from the Platform

NOTE: draft messages below may include dates, which need to be adjusted to appropriate cut-off dates.

Confirmation to Companies of Submission of a Challenge

When a company submits a Challenge for a review it gets an automatic email:

Dear Sir or Madam,

Thank you for submitting a Challenge on behalf of your company. Your Challenge is being reviewed by INDUSAC administrators. You will be notified about the progress.

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Companies about Published Challenges

When a Challenge is published, the company gets an automatic email:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The Challenge <title of the Challenge> you submitted on behalf of your company <name of company> has been approved and published on the INDUSAC website <embedded or added link to the website>

INDUSAC partners and other participating organisations (public universities and research institutions) will be promoting it through different media and channels among students and researchers.

We will be collecting applications / Motivation Letters from student / researcher co-creation teams until 11.02.2024, 23:59. In February 2024 you will be asked to select one or more co-creation team(s) that you wish to work with (as indicated in your Challenge).

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Companies about Received Motivation Letters

When the INDUSAC has completed pre-selection, links to selected Motivation Letters are sent to the respective company for evaluation, along with instructions on how to select the co-creation team via the INDUSAC platform:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The INDUSAC has received Solution proposals (Motivation Letters) for your Challenge. You may access the Motivation Letters at the following links

<links to Motivation Letters>

Please review the Motivation Letters and when finished, proceed to select on the INDUSAC platform the co-creation team(s) who will be solving your Challenge no later than 23.02.2024, 23:59 CET. Further instructions are on the platform (Annex 10).

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to companies that the FSTP declaration has been Signed

Dear Sir or Madam,

Thank you for selecting a co-creation team. We would like to inform you that the administrative procedures with the co-creation team have been completed. You may now get in contact with the co-creation team and arrange the kick-off meeting.

Please follow this [<link>](#) to a private chat with the co-creation team. This is the [<link>](#) to the INDUSAC library where you will find templates to assist the team in preparing the deliverables and a To-Do list (a Mentoring Plan) that the team may use as guidance to solve the Challenge.

The team may start working on a Challenge and should submit their Solution no later than 02.05.2024, 23:59 CET.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Companies to Evaluate the Solution and Fill out the Questionnaire

Once a co-creation team submits a Solution, the company is notified via the platform to evaluate the Solution and fill out the questionnaire:

Dear Sir or Madam,

The co-creation team has delivered a Solution for your challenge <title of Challenge>. Please find the uploaded documents here <links to Solution>.

We ask you to review the documents and give feedback. Further instructions are on the platform (Annex 11).

We also ask you to fill in the satisfaction questionnaire found at the following link: <link to the 1ka survey for companies>

We would like to receive your feedback no later than 15.5.2024, 23:59 CET.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

ANNEX 13 : Notifications that Students and Researchers Receive from the Platform

NOTE: draft messages below may include dates, which need to be adjusted to appropriate cut-off dates.

Team-member confirmation of Motivation Letter and participation in the co-creation team (for students and researchers)

Once a student/researcher starts to prepare a Motivation Letter, two checkpoints are made before submission: (1) the student/researcher needs to be registered on the INDUSAC platform, and (2) once registered, the student/researcher needs to assemble a co-creation team in order to be able to submit a Motivation Letter. Notifications covering these instances are listed below:

Dear Co-creation Team Member,

Your team leader has submitted the Motivation Letter for the Challenge <Challenge title> for your approval.

Please review and confirm the Motivation Letter and your participation in this co-creation team no later than: 11.02.2024, 23:59 CET. Until you have approved the Motivation Letter, it cannot be submitted to INDUSAC.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Team members invite other students / researchers do join the co-creation team

Dear <recipient name>,

I'm putting together a co-creation team of students/researchers that is applying to solve a Challenge _____ (Title of the Challenge) from company _____ (name of the company) from _____ (country). For details, please click here: _____ (insert the link to the Challenge) and I would like to have you as a teammate.

Would you like to join the international team of students and researchers to solve a Challenge? Please, register here <embed or add link>.

Official call for students/researchers and all the terms are published in the INDUSAC website: <https://indusac.eu/open-call-for-students-researchers/>.

Kind regards,

Notification to Students/Researchers of Receipt of Motivation Letter

Once the last co-creation team member confirms the Motivation Letter, all co-creation team members receive an e-mail:

Dear Co-creation Team Member,

Thank you for submitting your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> as part of the co-creation team comprising <name of team leader>, <name of member #1>, and <name of member #2>!

Please click on the link below to confirm the Motivation Letter:

<link>

After the submission deadline, your Motivation Letter will be revised. You will be notified about the result by 01.03.2024, at which time you will also receive instructions on how to proceed.

In case of questions, please consult the FAQ section (<embed or add link>) or contact us at [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification of Students/Researchers about the Approval or Rejection of Motivation Letter

If the Motivation Letter has been Accepted

Dear Co-creation Team Members,

INDUSAC is happy to inform you that your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> has been accepted by the company. The student members of your team may proceed to signing a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) Declaration. This declaration outlines the formal aspect of the financial support for students. The FSTP declaration needs to be signed digitally within seven (7) days from receiving this message. Please follow this <link> to fill in the data (bank details, etc.) and sign the document.

Once the FSTP Declaration is signed by all student members of the co-creation team, no later than 07.03.2024, 23:59 CET, all co-creation team members and the company will be notified with the timeline. You may then get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac@ijs.si.

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

If the Motivation Letter has been Rejected

Dear Co-creation Team Members,

INDUSAC regrets to inform you that your Motivation Letter to the Challenge <Challenge title> has not been approved. Please find below the justification:

<justification (see Annex 10)>

You are welcome to submit further Motivation Letters, as per the rules set out in the Call for Students and Researchers, by the next cut-off date. The available Challenges can be found at the INDUSAC platform: <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/challenges>.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to indusac@ijs.si.

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Invitation to Students to Sign a FSTP Declaration

Dear Co-creation Team Members,

Please proceed to signing a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) Declaration. This declaration outlines the formal aspect of the financial support for students. The FSTP declaration needs to be signed digitally within seven (7) days from receiving this message and no later than 07.03.2024, 23:59 CET. Please follow this <link> to fill in the data (bank details, etc.) and sign the document.

Once the FSTP Declaration is signed by all student members of the co-creation team, all co-creation team members and the company will be notified with the timeline. You may then get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.

In case of questions please check the FAQ section or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Confirmation for Students that the FSTP Declaration has been Signed

Dear Co-creation Team Members,

Thank you for signing the FSTP Declaration. You may now get in contact with the company and arrange the kick-off meeting.

Please go to the INDUSAC platform → My Activity, or follow this [<link>](#) to a private chat with the company. On this [<link>](#) is the INDUSAC library where you will find templates to assist you in preparing the deliverables and a To-Do list (a Mentoring Plan) that you may use as guidance to solve the Challenge.

Please start working on a Challenge and submit your Solution no later than 02.05.2024.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

Notification to Students/Researchers about Deadline for Submission of Solution

If Solutions have not been submitted one week before the deadline, co-creation team members receive the following email:

Dear Co-creation Team Members,

This is a kind reminder that you have to submit your Solution and the Co-creation Implementation Report in one week's time.

In case of questions please check FAQ or send an e-mail to [indusac\(at\)ijs.si](mailto:indusac(at)ijs.si).

Best regards,

INDUSAC partners

ANNEX 14 : Skill Level Survey for Students/Researchers before the Project

Questions for co-creation team members upon receiving info about approval of the Motivation Letter (before the start of the co-creation project):

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results-oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working with international teams
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills would you like to develop/improve:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation
 - Results oriented thinking
 - Responsibility
 - Creativity

- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working with international teams
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan
- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas

- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

ANNEX 15 : Questionnaire for Students/Researchers after Completion of the Co-creation Project

The purpose of the questionnaire is to evaluate the level of upskilling achieved during the co-creation project.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working in international teams
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills were significantly developed / improved through the co-creation team project:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation

- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working in international teams
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan

- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

Please, evaluate your experience in terms of clarity and satisfaction with the process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
finding the detailed information about the Challenge		
user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)		
method assistance through explanations and templates		
assistance through the proposed process and milestones		
registration on the platform		
creation of a team		

...continues on following page

...continued from previous page

Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
timeline of challenge application process		
timeline for solving the challenge		
submission of application / Motivation Letter		
working in a team - with other students / researchers		
working in a team - with company		
preparation of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
submission of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
(students only) financial transaction process		

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Collaboration

How often did you meet the company representative?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more than once a week

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

How often did you meet with your team members?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more than once a week

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

Did you benefit from working in a multicultural team?

1) Not at all 2) a bit 3) neutral 4) Yes I did 5) Yes a lot

Rate the level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Strongly Disagree" and 5 represents "Strongly Agree."

- The co-creation mechanism encouraged active participation and engagement from all participants.
- The co-creation process encouraged collaboration and co-learning among the participants.
- The co-creation process incorporated customer research and insights to understand the end-users' needs and preferences.
- The co-creation process fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating perspectives from social sciences and humanities to other disciplines.
- We, as a team, were encouraged to explore ethical considerations and social impact when generating ideas during the co-creation process.
- I was able to participate equally in the decision-making process.
- The co-creation process resulted in solutions that specifically addressed gender-related issues or considerations.
- Overall, the co-creation process successfully prioritised the human aspect (Inclusivity, Gender dimension, Interdisciplinarity, User Perspective, Collaboration, Iterative Feedback, Ethical Considerations) and created a meaningful and inclusive environment.

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Please, evaluate your current level of agreement with the following statements (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**) + option "I didn't use it":

- Help desk assistance (e.g. value of support received) was adequate.
- It is likely you would recommend participation in such a program to other peers
- Challenges were diverse enough and you were able to find an interesting one fast and start the co-creation process
- The Challenges were well described.

- Companies' expectations were reasonable.
- You are satisfied with the results that your co-creation team submitted,
- You benefited from working in an international environment.

Open questions:

- Appropriateness of funding: did you find funding appropriate, high enough? Were you able to cover all your costs? Considering actual costs and given rational consideration, do you feel that the funding received would be sufficient for supporting more than one co-creation project?
- What is the main reason you applied to INDUSAC open calls (money, connections to students and/or companies/researchers, international experiences, new skills etc.)?
- How would you rate (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale) your overall experience with the provided method recommendations and explanations, templates, process and milestone recommendations?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, provide an email address and the communication team will contact you for more information.

ANNEX 16 : Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-creation Project**Questions for company representatives after submission of the final report**

Name of your company

Title of your Challenge

Enter the ID of the co-creation team that worked on this Challenge (visible on top of their Motivation Letter)

In the following section (next three questions), please evaluate the co-creation team's Solution.

There are three categories with the following weights:

The company evaluates the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

Deliverable quality, max 10 points, weight 30 %, amounting to max 3 points

Business / Technical performance indicators, max 10 points, weight 60 %, amounting to max 6 points

Deadline compliance, max 10 points, weight 10 %, amounting to max 1 point

Scoring system for unweighed points:

0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects

1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly

3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly

5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved

7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved

9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points total) will receive payment.

Please evaluate Deliverable quality, scoring from lowest (0) to highest (3)

Please evaluate Business / Technical performance indicators, scoring from lowest (0) to highest (6)

Please evaluate Deadline compliance, award 1 point for Solution submitted on time

Please select a final decision on the Solution

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

Satisfaction with following steps of the whole process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale** + option “I didn’t use it”)

- publishing the challenge
- registration on the platform
- user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)
- experience of the offline modules (support material and libraries) of the platform
- communication with the co-creation team
- adequateness of timeline between posting and start of challenge
- adequateness of timeline for solving the challenge
- revision of applications / motivation letters
- assisting co-creation team in carrying out the project
- preparation of deliverables, reports, etc.
- submission of deliverables, reports, etc.
- punctuality of deliverable submission

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Satisfaction with the Solution and work of the co-creation team (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good – **Likert Scale**)

- Technical performance indicators:
 - Innovativeness: How do you estimate the innovative potential of the Solution?
 - Creativity: How do you evaluate the creativity of the Solution?
 - Improvement: How do you evaluate the performance of the Solution compared with your actual/previous solution (if not existent with a competitor's solution)?
- Business performance indicators:
 - Market potential: How do you evaluate the market potential of the Solution?
 - Relevancy: How do you evaluate the relevance of the Solution?
- Quality
 - Soundness: How do you evaluate the soundness of the work of the co-creation team?
 - Quality of work: How do you evaluate the quality of the work of the co-creation team?
 - Satisfaction: How satisfied are you with the work of the co-creation team?
- Will you use the Solution provided by the co-creation team within your company (No, definitely not – probably not – not decided yet – yes we will – yes, we already started)?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Have all requested deliverables been delivered by the co-creation team?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”

“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time, I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute with my ideas and knowledge. This really was a valuable experience.”

Please provide a short description of the project results - Solution provided by the team (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include confidential information.

On a scale of 1 to 5, how likely is it that you would recommend participation in this type of programme to your peers?

(1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good)

ANNEX 17 : Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners**STATEMENT ON
NON-DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION
AND IMPARTIALITY**

This statement pertains to procedures and activities carried out within the INDUSAC project.

This is to certify that I, the undersigned:

<Name and Surname>

<Home Address>

<Post Number and Town / City>

<State / Country>,

employed at:

<organisation>

member of the INDUSAC consortium

undertake that I shall not disclose confidential information (such as applications, work results, and personal data in connection to the INDUSAC piloting), acquired through activities within the INDUSAC Committee(s), through gathering and processing of data related to companies' and personal information regarding co-creation team applications, their work and their results, to unauthorised persons.

I hereby also confirm that I am not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters Challenges / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with INDUSAC partners and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Challenges / Solutions.

The obligations stated herein shall remain in force for a term of seven (7) years as from the date of signing hereof, and may be prolonged if the activities concerning the confidential data, as defined in this statement, continue after the expiration of this period.

This statement has been signed in 2 (two) identical paper copies, where one is for the signatory and one for the INDUSAC coordinator. The statement can be signed also electronically.

Place _____, date _____

Signature: _____

ANNEX 18 : INDUSAC Declaration of Financial Support to Third Parties**INDUSAC DECLARATION
on Financial Support to Third Parties**

We, the undersigned,

Co-creation Team member 1 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 2 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 3 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 4 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 5 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 6 (student)

First Name

Family name

Address (street, house number, country)

Residency (country)

Tax number from the country of residency

Gender

E-mail

Month / year of study start

Name of public university where you study

Country of the university

Bank Details

Bank Name and Bank Address

Transaction Account

IBAN

SWIFT Code of Bank

Members of team ID:

<ID team>

hereby declare that:

- we have established a cooperation, within the Horizon Europe INDUSAC project, with the INDUSAC project coordinator, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, with the intention of solving a Challenge entitled <Title of the Challenge>
- issued by a company <company name>
within a time frame of 4-8 weeks;
- we comprise a co-creation team represented by a co-creation team leader and at least two additional student/researchers, wherein all members of the co-creation team share equal treatment and responsibilities;
- the co-creation team, in addition to the listed students, comprises the following researchers as well:
 - o Name and Family name of researcher 1
 - o Name and Family name of researcher 2
 - o Name and Family name of researcher 3
 - o Name and Family name of researcher 4
 - o Name and Family name of researcher 5
- we accept the terms and conditions of the Call for Students and Researchers published on the INDUSAC website
- we accept the financial support to third parties, provided by the INDUSAC project coordinator, and in the amount of up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team and up to 1,000 EUR gross per individual student, based on financial support eligibility terms listed in the Call for Students and Researchers

The declaration shall enter into force on the date on which it is signed by all parties.

The declaration must be signed digitally.

Place, date _____

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 1 (student)
(student)

Name of co-creation Team Member 4

Place, date _____

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 2 (student)
(student)

Name of co-creation Team Member 5

Place, date _____

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 3 (student)
(student)

Name of co-creation Team Member 6

ANNEX 19 : TO DO List / Mentoring Plan Example

Example of a Mentoring Plan:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Task title	Input	Task description	Output/Deliverable	Deadline/Date	Template/Method	Process Phases Overview	
Get to know your team, the company and the challenge	Company details, Product introduction, Task description, Expectations	The company will present itself in a format they decide to give you an insight into the company history, its organizational structure, its products, or service portfolio and why they applied for this project. For your better understanding, the company's expectations and a task description will be presented with a Q&A session to ensure a clear understanding.	Clear understanding of the challenge	End of the first day of the challenge		Phase 0	
1. Warm up				Week 1		Phase 1	
1.1 Internal team assignment to tasks	To do list, INDUSAC list of methods and tools	Analyse the to do's necessary to solve the challenge. Assign teammates to tasks. Consider that for some tasks the company that hosts your challenge needs to be involved. Make sure to plan these tasks/ feedback rounds early on in the process.	Assignment of teammates to tasks; Scheduling of major tasks/ feedback with company (invites sent out/ appointments made)	Week 1		Phase 2	
1.2 Technical Set Up	INDUSAC Platform	Set up a place where you can work together collaboratively. You may just share a folder on e.g. Google Drive and sent the link within the INDUSAC chat to your teammates and the company representative. The company may also have an online storage space that can be used for your collaborative work that they can provide if they ask you to use their offer, make sure to do so, since it might be due to data protection regulations.	Shared Workspace (e.g. Google Drive folder)	Week 1		Phase 3	
1.3 Get to know the Company	Company's Website, Company's Input/Materials	First, visit the website and try to find out the following: Main facts about the company (founding year, employees, national/international)? What is the company selling (products, services...)? What kind of production/service is it (high-involvement, low-involvement, utilitarian, hedonic)? Which markets is the company targeting (mass market, niche markets)? Who is the main target of the product/service and is the target group aware of the product/service?		Week 1		Phase 4	
Let's tackle the challenge				Week 1 and 2		Phase 5	
2.1 Identify the product	Product description from the company, Research results	This task is for your understanding. To get to know the product you are working on, read through all provided material from the company. Further, do research on the internet or ask your acquaintances if they know or even used the product. You can also use the information you gathered in 1.3. Within this task, you can be creative with the visualization. Use all tools you want to, e.g. Mio, OneNotes, Mind maps or posters. Make sure every team member has access to the used tool.	Visualization of the product	Week 1		Phase 6	
2.2 Determine the properties	Technical description of the product (if provided by the company you may use it)	Create a list of relevant technical aspects such as the material, the size, and the weight. Look at all the components and try to understand how the technical properties match the function. If the company provides such a list you can use it. If you search on the internet make sure to use the right product variant. You can also implement the technical details in your output from 2.1.	Excel file with technical product details (product properties)	Week 2		Phase 7	
2.3 Research and Comparison	Product reviews, Consumer reports, Experts	Look at customer feedback and reviews to see what customers are saying about the product. This can give you insight into any issues or concerns that customers have with the product. You can ask the company if they provide you with a contact person for the marketing or sales office. Compare the product with similar products on the market. This will help you understand how the product stacks up against the competition. Through this task, you should find out if products from competitors have product properties that might be relevant for the company that hosts the challenge too.	Excel file with customer review compared to similar products	Week 2		Phase 8	
Milestone 1	Current findings	Present your findings to your company representative to make sure early on in the process, that you understood the product properties of the product that you focus on.	Feedback on current findings	End of Week 2		Phase 9	
M 1.1 Generate concept for milestone presentation	Current findings	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your current findings and next steps at the milestone.	One pager with concept for milestone presentation			Phase 10	
M 1.2 Preparation of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation, Current Findings	Preparation of milestone presentation and make sure the product properties are presented correctly and in an understandable way. If you want to present your Exec, put them in a ppt format to assure a smooth presentation.	PPT Milestone Presentation			Phase 11	
M 1.3 Dry run of pitch	PPT Milestone presentation	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to know the presentation and present it to the company representatives.	Be ready for Milestone			Phase 12	
M 1.4 Revising presentation and current findings	Feedback on Milestone Presentation	After the presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	New input for next steps (potential) revise and rework	Week 3		Phase 13	
Let's explore the future				Week 3		Phase 14	
3.1 Find out if your company provided you with scenarios	Scenarios	If the company has already identified scenarios, they will provide them to you and you can use them as a basis for analysis. Analyse the trends as well, and compare your findings with the provided scenarios. Make sure you have received them within the INDUSAC chat or in your shared workspace.	Information on basis of challenges, Scenario provided/tesho	Week 3		Phase 15	

3.1. Analysing trends and scenarios	Scenarios	Inform yourself in detail about the scenarios the company provided. First, analyse them and focus on the changes compared to the current situation. Then focus on the implications the scenario has for the product. For example a scenario describing urban mobility without any private cars. One implication for the product "passenger car" could be that the target customer is not a private customer but, for example, a taxi company. Discuss the findings within your group. How can the product be improved to fit into the different scenarios? What is relevant for the customer in the future? How does it affect the product in a technical way (e.g. load on the clutch and engine is different because customers do not care about the vehicle)? Write down your findings in tabular form. Research current trends using either one of the proposed websites or any other resource of trends that you might know. For your information: you might need to create an account to use the free test version of the trend websites. Try to understand the trends and research how they affect the product you are looking at. For example one trend describing autonomous driving. This could not only affect the product "passenger car" but also the customer target, for example a taxi company. Focus on 5-6 trends you consider most relevant for the product or branch of interest. Please make sure to also include an explanation of why you consider these trends to be the most relevant. Have you already noticed the trends? How would you act as a company knowing these trends?	Excel or PowerPoint table with current product specifications and future developments based on scenarios	Week 3	Scenario and Trend analysis - method and template
3.2. For teams with trends as basis	Scenarios	Research current trends using either one of the proposed websites or any other resource of trends that you might know. For your information: you might need to create an account to use the free test version of the trend websites. Try to understand the trends and research how they affect the product you are looking at. For example one trend describing autonomous driving. This could not only affect the product "passenger car" but also the customer target, for example a taxi company. Focus on 5-6 trends you consider most relevant for the product or branch of interest. Please make sure to also include an explanation of why you consider these trends to be the most relevant. Have you already noticed the trends? How would you act as a company knowing these trends?	Excel or PowerPoint table with current product specifications and future developments based on scenarios	Week 3	Scenario and Trend analysis - method and template. e.g. test versions of https://www.trend.com/en/indusac/milestones/usingtrend-robotar
Milestone 2	Current findings	Present your selected scenarios/trends as a starting point of your results to your company representative in an understandable way.	Feedback on current findings	End of Week 3	
M.2.1 Generate concept for milestone presentation	Current findings	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your results of scenarios and next steps at the milestone.	One pager with concept for milestone presentation		
M.2.2 Preparation of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation, Current Findings	Preparation of milestone presentation and make sure the product properties are presented correctly and in an understandable way. Present the possible development directions of the product (properties) regarding the scenarios or trends. Because this topic is more creative, you can choose a format you think fits best to give an understanding of your outcome.	Excel, PowerPoint, Miro, ...		
M.2.3 Dry run of pitch	Presentation format you chose in M.2.2	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to know the presentation and present it to the company representatives.	Be ready for Milestone		
M.2.4 Revising presentation and current findings	Feedback on Milestone Presentation	Milestone presentation After the presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	New input for next steps (potential) revises and rework	Week 4	
4. Deduct future-robust product properties				Week 4	
4.1. Deduct future-robust product properties from your findings	CS, Excel or PowerPoint with current product specifications and future developments	Develop with the information you collected on relevant trends (indoor scenarios) further product requirements. From these, you should derive product properties that are relevant in the context of each trend (scenario). Product properties are the characteristics of a product, while product requirements are the wanted characteristics by the customers. The product properties that are derived in the context of scenarios or trends can be seen as future-robust product properties if they appear in more than one scenario. How is the product specified now and what are the product properties that you now consider relevant for the future knowing these trends? Put the ideas in your CS, your Continuous Idea Storage. In your collaborative workspace. Example from 3.2.1 developed further: one implication for the product "passenger car" could be that the target customer is not a private customer but, for example, a taxi company. A possible future-robust product property would be the "possibility to insert separation between the driver and the passengers". What are the future-robust product properties that can be derived for the product from the trends or scenarios? To evaluate these properties create an Excel with all trends/scenarios. Insert all product properties and mark by which trend they are affected. With this, you can select the future-robust ones.	Extend your Excel or PowerPoint with product properties that you consider relevant for the future	Week 4	
4.2. Prioritizing future-robust product properties	Excel or PowerPoint with product properties	With the found future-robust product properties conduct a cost-benefit analysis to prioritize the product properties. Within this analysis, your team elaborates criteria by which the properties should be ranked. This will help you prioritize the properties. Therefore, you can use an Excel file.	Excel file	Week 4	
Final Milestone	Final results	The aim of this presentation is to show your results in an understandable way and to show the company your hard work and why it is so good.	Feedback on final results	End of Week 4	
FM 1 Generate concept for milestone presentation	Final results	Prepare a structured concept (one pager) which describes how you will present your results of the derived future-robust properties and how you derived them out of scenarios or trends (depending on 3.2). Think of how you can present your future-robust product properties from your findings in a way the company understands them, their relevance and how you came to them.	One pager with concept for milestone presentation		
FM 2 Preparation of milestone presentation	Concept for milestone presentation, Final results	For the presentation make a storyline to explain your process and hence, your results. You want to impress the representatives with your work from the last weeks.	Excel, PowerPoint, Miro, ...		
FM 3 Dry run of pitch	Presentation format you chose in FM 2	Train the presentation for the milestone and give constructive feedback to your team members to improve the presentation style and the slide deck. After your feedback revise your slide deck and assure to know the presentation and present it to the company representatives.	Be ready for Milestone		
FM 4 Revising presentation and results	Feedback on Milestone presentation	Milestone presentation After the final presentation, the company will give you feedback in oral/written form. If it is oral, please assure that (at least) one team member is writing everything down. Incorporate feedback into your final deliverables.	Revised presentation and results	Week 5	
5. Final submission				2 days after final presentation	
5.1 Submit solution	Final results, Report	Upload your deliverables on the INDUSAC platform in the respective space for it. If you have not yet written a report about the process, please do so and upload it with the other deliverables. In case you have files, that are too big to be uploaded, talk to the company and tell them where within the shared workspace you have to upload the deliverables. Please only do so if the upload on the INDUSAC platform in the respective fields is not possible.	Deliverables on INDUSAC platform		

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